

Systematic review protocol to identify Microbiological Hazards in Novel Foods

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Abstract

This document describes the Systematic Review Protocol to identify Microbiological Hazards in Novel Foods, which will be carried out within the framework of the procurement titled MICROHAZ – Microbiological Hazards in Novel Foods (reference NP/EFSA/NIF/2024/02).

Following the background section, the protocol presents the approach used to define the assessment questions and sub-questions, and describes the methodology to be used for the identification of microbiological hazards in novel foods.

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1 Background

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) is the keystone of the European Union's (EU) risk assessment (RA) regarding safety in the food chain from farm to fork. EFSA delivers independent and transparent scientific advice to policy makers, through cooperation with our partners, and in an open dialogue with society.

Under EU regulations, any food that was not used for human consumption to a significant degree within the Union before 15 May 1997 is considered a novel food (NF). The category covers new foods, food from new sources, new substances used in food as well as new ways and technologies for producing food. Since Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 on NFs came into force in January 2018, the process for scientific RA of NF applications has been centralised: EFSA performs RA on the safety of NFs upon request by the European Commission.

EFSA carries out its assessment based on dossiers provided by applicants, which should follow the Guidance on the scientific requirements for an application for authorisation of a novel food in the context of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283¹. Among others, information on microbiological contaminants (i.e., microbial hygiene indicators and pathogens) in the NF should be provided, considering the NF source, production process and regulatory requirements. Moreover, the scientific literature should be reviewed by taking into account systematic review principles (EFSA, 2010²) to retrieve published data relevant to the NF source, the part(s) used in/as NF and the production process, and even studies with similar foods from the same or other closely related sources or on foods with similar composition. The overall outcome of the RA process is published in the EFSA Journal in the form of a scientific opinion and made publicly available.

The EFSA Strategy 2027³ outlines the need to increase the risk analysis capabilities by harmonising RA and improving data quality, interoperability, and usability. Furthermore, with a growing number of novel food dossiers, new tools are necessary to support the RA process, making it more agile and ensuring quality and consistency.

With this background, EFSA launched a Procurement aimed to create an *in silico* tool to support the microbial RA of NFs performed by the Panel on Nutrition, Novel Foods and Food Allergens of EFSA. This Procurement, titled MICROHAZ – Microbiological Hazards in Novel Foods (reference NP/EFSA/NIF/2024/02) was designed and launched in the context of EFSA's 2024 Work Programme for grants and operational procurements as presented in Annex XII of the Programming Document 2024 – 2026, available on the EFSA's website.⁴

One of the objectives of this project is to carry out a Systematic Literature Review on the Microbiological Hazards relevant/associated to NF for which the protocol is described below.

¹ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/6555>

² <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/1637>

³ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-07/efsa-strategy-2027.pdf>

⁴ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-01/programming-document-2024-2026.pdf>

2 Approach

2.1 General considerations and scope

The term Novel Foods (**NFs**) will be limited to those products falling under Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 at the time the searches will be carried out (26/05/2025, including: (i) Authorized NFs included in the Union list⁵; (ii) NFs currently under suitability check or risk assessment by EFSA (summary / non-confidential version of the dossier available on the Open EFSA portal); (iii) Products with NF status following consultation pursuant to Article 4(2) of the Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 (https://food.ec.europa.eu/food-safety/novel-food/consultation-process-novel-food-status_en); and (iv) Products that will need an authorisation under the NF Regulation as per the EU NF status catalogue (<https://ec.europa.eu/food/food-feed-portal/screen/novel-food-catalogue/search>).

2.2 Systematic review and data extraction

2.2.1 Problem formulation

Taking into account the background of this procurement procedure and following the definitions and procedures of EFSA Guidance on protocol development for EFSA generic scientific assessments (EFSA SC, 2023), a mandate named **Microbiological safety of NFs** has been defined. This mandate has been translated into a Term of Reference:

- ToR 1: Hazardous microorganisms in NFs.

Likewise, this ToR has been translated into assessment questions (AQs) and sub-questions (SQs), as per the EFSA Guidance (EFSA SC, 2023). Figure 1 and Table 2 present the analysis of the mandate, including AQs and SQs, whose answers are envisaged to address EFSA's risk assessment needs concerning microbiological hazards in NFs.

As shown in Table 1, AQs and SQs are of descriptive nature as they enquire about a condition of interest (i.e., microbiological hazards and process hygiene indicators) in a food population (NFs). In most cases these questions have a simple PO (population and outcome) structure with key elements that can be broken down as follows:

AQ1 Occurrence of microbial hazards in NFs:

- Population: Novel Foods
- Outcome: Occurrence of a microbiological hazard

The only exception would be SQ1.1.1 and SQ1.1.2 which have a PI/EO (population; intervention/exposure; outcome) structure with key elements that can be broken down as follows.

- Population: NFs

⁵ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2470 of 20 December 2017 establishing the Union list of novel foods in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 of the European Parliament and of the Council on novel foods (Text with EEA relevance) C/2017/8878. *OJ L 351, 30.12.2017, p. 72–201*

- Intervention/Exposure: Food processing
- Outcome: Occurrence of a microbiological hazard.

Figure 1: Conceptual model including ToRs, Assessment Questions and Sub-Questions.

Table 2: Assessment question and sub-questions formulated using PI/ECO format

AQ(s) and SQs generically defined	Population (P)	Intervention or Exposure (I or E)	Comparison (C)	Outcome (O)	AQ(s) and SQs formulated
AQ1. Occurrence in NF	<i>Novel Foods</i>	<i>Not relevant for this AQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Occurrence of a microbiological hazard</i>	<i>what is the occurrence of the microbiological hazard "X" in the Novel Food "N"?</i>
SQ1.1. Concentration in NF	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>what is the concentration of the microbiological hazard "X" as per AQ1?</i>
SQ1.1.1. Stage of the food chain	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>at which each stage of the food chain is the concentration determined as per SQ1.1?</i>
SQ1.1.2. Critical parameters	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Process/food conditions</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which are the critical process/food parameters determining the concentration of the microbiological hazard as per SQ1.1?</i>
SQ1.2. Prevalence in NF	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>what is the prevalence of the microbiological hazard "X" as per AQ1?</i>
SQ1.2.1. Stage of the food chain	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>at which each stage of the food chain is the prevalence determined as per SQ1.2?</i>
SQ1.2.2. Critical parameters	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Process/food conditions</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which are the critical process/food parameters determining the prevalence of the microbiological hazard as per SQ1.2?</i>
SQ1.3. Source of hazardous microorganisms in NF	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>what is the source of the microbiological hazard "X" as per AQ1?</i>
SQ1.4. Sampling plan	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which sampling plan is used to determine the concentration or prevalence as per SQ 1.2 or SQ1.2</i>
SQ1.4.1. Sampling size	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which sampling size is used in the sampling plan as per SQ1.4?</i>
SQ1.5. Analytical method	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which is the analytical method used to determine the occurrence of the microbiological hazard "X" as per AQ1?</i>
SQ1.5.1. Regulatory reference method	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Is there any regulatory method for the microorganism tested?</i>
SQ1.5.2. LOQ/LOD	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which is the LOQ/LOD of the analytical method as per SQ1.5?</i>
SQ1.5.3. Sample size	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which is the size of the samples analysed used the analytical method as per SQ1.5?</i>
SQ1.5.4. Sensibility	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which is the sensibility of the analytical method as per SQ1.5?</i>
SQ1.5.5. Specificity	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which is the specificity of the analytical method as per SQ1.5?</i>
SQ1.6. Maximum allowable limit	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Not relevant for this SQ</i>	<i>Same as AQ1</i>	<i>which is the maximum allowable limit of the microbiological hazard "X" in the Novel Food "N" as per AQ1?</i>

2.2.2 Methodology to address AQ1 and related SQs

A systematic review (SR) will be conducted to address AQ1 and the corresponding SQs, i.e., to retrieve data related to the occurrence of microbiological hazards in NFs and related information according to Figure 1 and Table 2. SRs are a well-established evidence synthesis strategy for published research with a very well-defined methodology. In this type of review, a structured and reproducible process is followed to minimize the risk of bias in the results, thus providing more robust conclusions to inform further decision making (Higgins and Green, 2011).

The SR will be conducted strictly following the general principles for SR as specified by EFSA (2010) and PRISMA-S (Preferred Reporting Items for SR and Meta-Analyses) methodology -an extension to the Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in SR and considering the new paradigm proposed in the recent EFSA guidance on protocol development (EFSA SC, 2023).

2.2.2.1 Evidence retrieval

2.2.2.1.1 Sources of evidence

Scientific literature databases. The following databases will be used:

- PubMed/MEDLINE (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PubMed>)
- Web of Science (<https://www.webofknowledge.com>)
- SCOPUS (<https://www.scopus.com/>)

Reference lists. The reference list at the end of relevant publications will be checked to identify studies that have not been retrieved.

Grey literature. Sources included are listed below:

- Patents: Spacenet search engine (<https://worldwide.espacenet.com/>).
- Websites and on-going research and research results registers. Searches will be conducted in websites of relevant organizations (e.g. research organizations, working groups, commercial, stakeholders, and national agencies).
- As a source for NF specifications/characteristics:
 - Union list of authorized Novel Foods (https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/novel-food/authorisations/union-list-novel-foods_en).
 - EFSA Scientific Opinions on the safety of NFs
- As a source for NF production processes:
 - Repository of NF production processes reported by Martínez et al. (2024).
- As sources of regulations, analytical methods, and maximum admissible limits

- Websites and on-going research and research results registers. Searches will be conducted in websites of relevant organizations (e.g. research organizations, working groups, commercial, stakeholders, and national agencies).

2.2.2.1.2 Search strategy

Constraints in the search strategy

- Fields: Title, Abstract and Keywords
- Dates: No temporal constraint
- Languages: English
- Publication type: Primary research studies (i.e., studies generating new data), conference abstracts or posters if they contain primary data and PhD theses and dissertations.

Keywords and search strings

A dual search strategy will be developed including a “NF specific” and a “NF generic” search strategy/search strings. The list of keywords and the structured search strings are reported in Supplementary Material.

a) NF-specific search strategy

The “NF-specific” search strategy (Figure 2) is designed to narrow down the search on the NF under study (please refer to section 2.1) since the term “novel foods” is commonly used in the literature but not necessarily to describe products falling under Regulation (EU) 2015/2283. Thus, specific keywords defined for each NF under study (293) will be included in the first search block.

The second search block will include a series of keywords related to microbiological studies/microbial hazards.

The different search blocks will be combined in the search string by using the Boolean operator “AND” (Figure 2).

Figure 2: NF-specific search strings

Independent searches will be conducted for each NF.

b) NF-generic search strategy

The “NF generic” strategy is intended to complement the “NF-specific” one, towards a broader coverage of potentially relevant hits from the consulted literature sources. The following search blocks will be combined in the search string by using the Boolean operator “AND” (Figure 3):

- A list of keywords related to the “NF” definition (as per 2.1).
- A list of keywords related to microbiological studies/microbial hazards.

Figure 3: NF-generic search strings

2.2.2.2 Study selection process

Study selection will be performed and documented using the web-based systematic review software DistillerSR.

Searches will be carried out on the aforementioned databases, and then the search results/references will be imported to EndNote, which will be used to create the files to be exported to DistillerSR. The full search strings will be recorded exactly as performed, together with the number of records retrieved and the date of search. References from each of the NF-specific search strategy independent search will be labelled using DistillerSR according to the NF under study to facilitate the eligibility screening.

DistillerSR Duplicate Detection tool will be used to find and quarantine duplicates. Detection options will be applied sequentially (Title, authors, abstract).

Studies retrieved through the extensive literature searches will be screened for relevance using a two-step approach:

Title and abstract screening

In the first step, screening will be performed by two reviewers independently, based on the information contained in the title and abstract, and by applying the eligibility criteria indicated in table 3.

Articles marked as irrelevant by the two reviewers will be excluded without proceeding to the full-text analysis. In case of a lack of consensus among the reviewers or if the two experts have doubts about a specific document, a conservative approach will be followed to ensure completeness, and the document will be considered for full text screening.

Full-text screening

Full text of the publications considered relevant after the first step will be screened for inclusion/exclusion by two reviewers independently by applying the eligibility criteria indicated in table 4. Any disagreement will be reconciled by consulting a third reviewer, which will take the ultimate decision on inclusion or exclusion.

The resulting hits from each screening step will be reported including a flow chart following the provisions of the PRISMA statement (<https://www.prisma-statement.org/>), a structured framework ensuring the transparent and systematic reporting of reviews.

Each step of the article screening/selection process will be documented within the DistillerSR environment to assure transparency and reproducibility.

The shortlisted included and excluded studies and the reasons of selection will also be provided.

Table 3: Title and Abstract screening exclusion criteria

Description of the exclusion criteria	Exclusion code
<i>Documents to be excluded according to publication characteristics (abstract not available or not in English; reviews, books and book chapters, letters to the editor, or other type of documents not containing primary data....)</i>	EC 1
<i>Studies/experiments not reporting/quantifying microbiological hazards and/or indicators of them</i>	EC 2
<i>Studies not associated to NFs as defined in 2.1.1</i>	EC 3
<i>Documents with general speculation, general description or historical description of NFs or microbiological hazards, or any other document not directly related to the that cannot be excluded according to the above-mentioned criteria</i>	EC 4

Table 4: Full text screening exclusion criteria

Description of the exclusion criteria	Exclusion code
<i>Documents to be excluded according to report characteristics (full text not available or not in English; reviews, books and book chapters, letters to the editor...)</i>	EC 1
<i>Studies/experiments not reporting/quantifying microbiological hazards and/or indicators of them</i>	EC 2
<i>Studies not associated to NFs as defined in 2.1.1 or where food chain stage/storage period where/when samples were taken for analysis is not specified</i>	EC 3
<i>Studies not presenting results on prevalence (sample size and number of positive samples) or concentration (sample size and measure of concentration)</i>	EC 4
<i>Microbiological method not indicated/referenced</i>	EC 5
<i>Documents with general speculation, general description, or historical description of NF, or microbial hazards, or any other document that cannot be included according to the eligibility criteria and cannot be excluded according to the above-mentioned criteria</i>	EC 6

2.2.2.3 Data extraction from included studies

Specifically designed Excel spreadsheets will be used for data extraction.

Data will be organized based on the AOs and SQs to ensure relevant information is easily accessible and structured for analysis.

The information collected from the included studies will be the following:

- Bibliographic information:

- o Title
- o Abstract
- o Author
- o DOI
- o URL
- o Item type
- o Name of the bibliographic source
- o Language
- o Volume
- o Pages
- o Year

- Product name and categories/classification:

- o NF product (including species and variety)
- o NF category (according to 258/97 or 2015/2283).
- o NF status (authorized, Under RA/suitability check, consultation process).
- o NF origin (animal, plant, fungi, synthetic...)
- o NF intended use: Whole/Ingredient/Supplement and food categories.

- Product characteristics:

- o NF Form (powder, syrup, solution...)
- o NF physico-chemical characteristics (per food chain stage and/or storage time)
 - pH
 - aw
- o NF composition (per food chain stage and/or storage time)
 - Nutritional
 - Other components of relevance
- o Processing steps
 - Processes or technologies applied
 - Processing/operational parameters/conditions
- o Shelf-life
 - Proposed shelf-life
 - Storage conditions
 - Temperature
 - Packaging
 - Light exposure
 - Oxygen/atmosphere
 - Relative humidity

- Microbiological Hazard:

- o Biological hazard (including species and group/serogroup...)
- o Type (pathogen or indicator)
- o Concentration/Prevalence (per food chain stage and/or storage time)
- o Source
- o Maximum limits suggested/reported
- Sampling plan (when reported (e.g. for observational studies)):
 - o Sampling plan
 - o Sampling size
- Analytical method:
 - o Name and description of the method
 - o Regulatory reference method
 - o Sample size
 - o LOQ/LOD
 - o Sensibility
 - o Specificity

Number of reviewers: two, one for data extraction and one for validating the extracted data.

Disagreements: In case of borderline data to extract, a conservative approach will be used to ensure that no information is lost. Data will be checked by a third member of the team for confirmation.

For quantitative data, individual counts will be retrieved. When required, WebPlotDigitalizer will be used to extract quantitative data from figures.

2.2.2.4 Evidence Appraisal

The methodological quality of each included study will be critically appraised. Each study will undergo a standardized assessment, checking whether it met a predefined list of characteristics. This information will be embedded in the same file for data extraction indicated in the previous section.

Two independent reviewers will score each study against risk of bias. The following issues will be analyzed: Selection bias, Detection bias, Reporting bias and Other bias (the later one including methodological quality assessment). The studies will be judged on three categories of bias: high, low and unclear. As a criterion, a global risk of bias score will not be used; instead, articles for which a high risk is determined in any of the four evaluated aspects will be excluded. Disagreements regarding scores will be resolved by discussion and consultation with a third reviewer when needed.

2.2.2.5 Protocol for grey literature search and screening

A specific methodology for searching, documenting, reporting and selecting grey literature will be applied according to Godin et al. (2015). Nevertheless, similarly to other information sources, grey literature followed SR reporting standards as established in the PRISMA statement (Moher et al., 2009).

- Patents

The search strings used for the standard literature review will be translated into Spacenet syntax. Eligibility criteria will be the same as those for other information sources.

The study selection, data extraction and evidence appraisal processes will be carried out as described in 2.2.2.2, 2.2.2.3 and 2.2.2.4.

2.2.2.6 Evidence synthesis/integration

The information retrieved will be used to build a database based on a Data model to be designed.

3 Acknowledgements

This work will be undertaken as part of the European Food Safety Authority tender NP/EFSA/NIF/2024/02: MICROHAZ – Microbiological Hazards in Novel Foods.

4 Disclaimer

The present document has been produced and adopted by the bodies identified above as author(s). This task has been carried out exclusively by the author(s) in the context of a contract between the European Food Safety Authority and the author(s), awarded following a tender procedure. The present document is published complying with the transparency principle to which the Authority is subject. It may not be considered as an output adopted by the Authority. The European Food Safety Authority reserves its rights, view and position as regards the issues addressed and the conclusions reached in the present document, without prejudice to the rights of the authors.

5 Conflicts of interest statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest in relation to the published work. All interests declared by the authors have been scrutinised by the European Food Safety Authority as part of the tender process to assesses whether a declared interest constitutes a conflict.

6 CRediT author statement

GC: Conceiving the review; designing the review; coordinating the review; data collection; data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; writing the protocol. MG: Data collection; data management; reviewing the protocol. VA: Data collection; data management; reviewing the protocol. MH: Data collection; data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol. IA: Data collection; data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol. VC: Data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol. UGB: Data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol. AB: Data collection; data management; reviewing the protocol. AP: Data collection; data management; reviewing the protocol. RMGG: Data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol. GDPI: Data collection; data management; reviewing the protocol. MSG: Data collection;

data management; reviewing the protocol. AV: Data collection; data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol. FPR: Data collection; data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol. EC: Conceiving the review; designing the review; data collection; data management; analysis of data; interpretation data; reviewing the protocol.

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